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DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION
DEVI AHILYA UNIVERSITY
INDORE**

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Comparative study of Somatotypes of selected Indian elite male jumpers and throwers

Brij Bhushan Singh, Dau Dayal Yadav and Jaswant Singh Yadav

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ABSTRACT

This study is an attempt to investigate the differences existing in the Somatotypes of elite male Indian high jumpers, Long jumpers, Triple jumpers, Pole vaulters, Shot putters, Discus throwers, Javelin throwers and Hammer throwers. Heath Carter (1990) method was used to determine the Somatotype of elite Indian male jumpers and throwers of different events. Analysis of variance and LSD test were used to assess the significant difference in the groups. Results showed significantly greater mean Endomorphy and Mesomorphy of Shot put and mean Ectomorphy of high jump having significantly greater than other groups.

Singh, Brij Bhushan; Yadav, Dau Dayal and Yadav, Jaswant Singh (2012) Comparative study of somatotypes of selected Indian elite male jumpers and throwers *International Journal of Physical Education Sports and Yogic Sciences* 1(3): 1-5.

Key Words: Somatotypes, Endomorphy, Mesomorphy and Ectomorphy.

The measurements of different body dimensions and ratios are of great relevance to the physical activity, especially in sports. The anthropometric assessment of physique involves the use of carefully defined body landmarks, specific positioning of the subject and use of appropriate instruments. The measurements that are taken on an individual are highly objective and highly reliable in the hand of a trained anthropometrist. The Competitive sports demand event specific physique and body composition to achieve the success. De Garay *et al.* (1974) concluded that top-level performance in a particular event demands a particular type of body size and shape, if other aspects are being similar. Hirata (1966) suggested that a nation with people whose general physique is limited to the characteristics of champions in certain events must concentrate their sports training on those specific events only. This study is an attempt to investigate the differences existing in the somatotype profile of elite male Indian jumpers and throwers of different athletes.

$$\text{Endomorphy} = -0.7182 + 0.1451 \times \sum SF - 0.00068 \times \sum SF^2 + 0.0000014 \times \sum SF^3$$

[Where SF = sum of triceps, sub scapular and suprailiac skin fold multiplied by 170.18/height in centimeter]

$$\text{Mesomorphy} = 0.858 \times \text{Humerus breadth} + 0.601 \times \text{Femur breadth} + 0.188 \times \text{*Corrected arm girth} + 0.161 \times \text{*Corrected calf girth} - \text{height} \times 0.131 + 4.5$$

(* Subtract the triceps skin fold and calfskin fold from the arm girth and calf girth, respectively).

Ectomorphy was determined by comparing the calculated height, weight ratio (HWR) of the subject with the underline values given below.

Methodology:

The purpose of this research work is to find out significant difference in the Somatotype of elite 200 male subjects of (25 each Shot put, Discus, Javelin, Hammer, High jump, Long jump, Triple Jump and Pole Vault) Indian male jumpers and throwers of different jumping and throwing events. Anthropometric data required in Heath-Carter method (1990) was collected from the selected elite jumpers and thrower of different events from SAI hostels All India Intervarsity athletic meets, Senior National federation cup and Asian All star Athletic meet. Heath Carter rating for Endomorphy, Mesomorphy and Ectomorphy was the criterion measure of this study.

SOMATOTYPE

The following Heath and Carter (1990) method was applied to determine Somatotype of subjects:

$$\text{HWR} = \frac{\text{Height in cm}}{\sqrt[3]{\text{Weight in kg}}}$$

If HWR is greater than or equal to 40.75 than ectomorphy = 0.732 * HWR - 28.58

➤ If HWR is less than 40.75 and greater than 39.65 then ectomorphy = 0.463*HWR-17.68

If HWR is equal to or less than 39.65 than ectomorphy = 0.5

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Results and Discussion:

Table - I: Endomorphy

S.V.	d. f.	S.S.	M.S.S.	F-value
Treatment	7	226.2222	32.31745	52.19354*
Error	192	118.8835	0.619185	

*Significant at .05 level $\text{tab}F_{0.05}(7, 192) = 2.05$

Since calculated F value is $>$ tab F, there was significant difference in the mean Endomorphy of long, high and triple jumpers, pole vaulters, shot putters, Discus, Javelin and Hammer Throwers. To analyze which group's mean was greater than other L.S.D. test was applied.

Table - II: Treatment means arranged in order of magnitude

Throwing and jumping groups								Mean difference	CD at 5% level
S T	H T	D T	J T	L J	P V	H J	T J		
4.536	4.169							0.367*	0.366
4.536		4.084						0.452*	0.366
4.536			3.278					1.258*	0.366
4.536				2.026				2.510*	0.366
4.536					2.025			2.512*	0.366
4.536						1.975		2.561*	0.366
4.536							1.942	2.594*	0.366
	4.169	4.084						0.085	0.366
	4.169		3.278					0.891*	0.366
	4.169			2.026				2.143*	0.366
	4.169				2.025			2.145*	0.366
	4.169					1.975		2.194*	0.366
	4.169						1.942	2.227*	0.366
		4.084	3.278					0.806*	0.366
		4.084		2.026				2.058*	0.366
		4.084			2.025			2.059*	0.366
		4.084				1.975		2.109*	0.366
		4.084					1.942	2.142*	0.366
			3.278	2.026				1.252*	0.366
			3.278		2.025			1.253*	0.366
			3.278			1.975		1.303*	0.366
			3.278				1.942	1.336*	0.366
				2.026	2.025			0.001	0.366
				2.026		1.975		0.051	0.366
				2.026			1.942	0.084	0.366
					2.025	1.975		0.050	0.366
					2.025		1.942	0.082	0.366
						1.975	1.942	0.032	0.366

*Significant at 5% level

Table - II shows that mean Endomorphy of Shot putters was $>$ Hammer, Discus, Javelin throwers, Pole vaulters, High, long and Triple jumpers. Further mean Endomorphy of hammer throwers and discus throwers were $>$ Javelin throwers, pole vaulters, high, long and triple jumpers. Mean endomorphy of javelin throwers is $>$ pole vaulters, high, long and triple jumpers. However the mean Endomorphy of Hammer and discus throwers, pole vaulters, high, long and triple jumpers have insignificant difference among them.

Table - III: Mesomorphy

S. V.	d. f.	S.S.	M.S.S.	F-value
Treatment	7	145.6346	20.80494	17.46199*
Error	192	228.7567	1.191441	

*Significant at .05 level $\text{Tab} F_{0.05}(7, 192) = 2.05$

Since cal F value was $>$ tab F value, the hypothesis was rejected and significant difference existed in the mean mesomorphy of high, long, and triple jumpers, pole vaulters, shot putters, discus, javelin and hammer throwers. To find group means of mesomorphy was $>$ other, pair wise means LSD test was used.

Table - IV: Treatment means arranged in order of magnitude

Throwing and jumping groups								Mean difference	CD at 5% level
S T	TJ	LJ	PV	DT	HJ	HT	JT		
5.035	3.798							1.237*	0.508
5.035		3.679						1.356*	0.508
5.035			3.626					1.409*	0.508
5.035				3.45				1.585*	0.508

5.035					2.525			2.510*	0.508
5.035						2.397		2.638*	0.508
5.035							2.347	2.688*	0.508
	3.798	3.679						0.119	0.508
	3.798		3.626					0.172	0.508
	3.798			3.45				0.348	0.508
	3.798				2.525			1.273*	0.508
	3.798					2.397		1.401*	0.508
	3.798						2.347	1.451*	0.508
		3.679	3.626					0.053	0.508
		3.679		3.45				0.229	0.508
		3.679			2.525			1.154*	0.508
		3.679				2.397		1.282*	0.508
		3.679					2.347	1.332*	0.508
			3.626	3.45				0.176	0.508
			3.626		2.525			1.101*	0.508
			3.626			2.397		1.229*	0.508
			3.626				2.347	1.279*	0.508
				3.45	2.525			0.925*	0.508
				3.45		2.397		1.053*	0.508
				3.45			2.347	1.103*	0.508
					2.525	2.397		0.128	0.508
					2.525		2.347	0.178	0.508
						2.397	2.347	0.05	0.508

*Significant at 5% level

Table - IV shows that mean Mesomorphy of shot putters is significantly > high, triple, long jumpers, pole vaulters, discus, hammer and javelin throwers. Further mean Mesomorphy of Triple jumpers, Long jumpers, Pole vaulters and discus throwers are > High jumpers, hammer and javelin throwers. However the Mean mesomorphy of Triple jumper is < pole vaulter and discus thrower. Further the mean mesomorphy long jumpers > discus throwers. Mean mesomorphy of pole vaulters > discus throwers, The mean mesomorphy of high jumpers is < hammer and javelin throwers. And the mean mesomorphy of hammer is < javelin throwers.

Table - VI: Treatment means arranged in order of magnitude

Throwing and jumping groups								Mean difference	CD at 5% level
H J	T J	P V	L J	J T	D T	H T	S T		
4.323	3.131							1.192*	0.329
4.323		2.839						1.484*	0.329
4.323			2.552					1.771*	0.329
4.323				1.717				2.606*	0.329
4.323					1.303			3.020*	0.329
4.323						0.875		3.736*	0.329
4.323							0.587	3.736*	0.329
	3.131	2.839						0.292	0.329
	3.131		2.552					0.579*	0.329
	3.131			1.717				1.414*	0.329
	3.131				1.303			1.828*	0.329
	3.131					0.875		2.256*	0.329
	3.131						0.587	2.544*	0.329
		2.839	2.552					0.288	0.329
		2.839		1.717				1.123*	0.329
		2.839			1.303			1.536*	0.329

Table - V: Ectomorphy

S. V.	D. F.	S.S.	M.S.S.	F-value
Treatment	7	282.265	40.32357	0.6591*
Error	192	95.98576	65535	

*Significant at .05 level $\text{tab } F_{0.05}(7, 192) = 2.05$

Since $\text{cal } F > \text{tab } F$, the hypothesis is rejected and significant difference exist in the mean ectomorphy of High, Long, Triple jumpers, Pole vaulters, Shot putters, Discus, Javelin and Hammer throwers. To find which group means of ectomorphy is greater than the other, paired means analysis is done using LSD test.

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		2.839				0.875		1.964*	0.329
		2.839					0.587	2.252*	0.329
			2.552	1.717				0.835*	0.329
			2.552		1.303			1.248*	0.329
			2.552			0.875		1.677*	0.329
			2.552				0.587	1.964*	0.329
				1.717	1.303			0.413*	0.329
				1.717		0.875		0.842*	0.329
				1.717			0.587	1.129*	0.329
					1.303	0.875		0.428*	0.329
					1.303		0.587	0.716*	0.329
						0.875	0.587	0.287	0.329

*Significant at 5% level

Table - VI shows that mean ectomorphy of High jumpers is significantly > Triple jumpers, Pole vaulters, Long jumpers, Javelin, Discus, Hammer throwers and Shot putters. Further mean ectomorphy of triple jumpers and pole vaulters are also significantly > Long jumpers, Javelin, discus, hammer throwers and shot putters. The mean ectomorphy of long jumpers is significantly > javelin, discus, hammer

throwers and shot putters. The mean ectomorphy of the javelin throwers is significantly > discus, hammer throwers and shot putters. The mean ectomorphy of the discus throwers is also > shot putters. However the mean ectomorphy of the triple jumpers is < pole vaulters, and the mean ectomorphy of the pole vaulters is < long jumpers. The mean ectomorphy of the hammer throwers is < shot putters.

Figure 1: Mean Endomorphy, Mesomorphy, and Ectomorphy ratings of different jumpers and throwers (ST= Shot putters, DT=Discus throwers, JT= Javelin throwers, HT=Hammer throwers, HJ=High jumpers, LJ=Long jumpers, TJ=Triple jumpers and PV=Pole vaulters).

Endomorphy

The result showed that mean Endomorphy of Shot putters was significantly > Endomorphy of Hammer, Discus, Javelin throwers, Pole vaulters, High, Long and Triple jumpers. Further mean Endomorphy of hammer and discus throwers were significantly > of Javelin throwers, pole vaulters, high, long and triple jumpers. Mean endomorphy of javelin throwers was significantly > of pole vaulters, high, long and triple jumpers.

Shot putter need maximum explosive strength for putting the shot to greater distance, for this they require great muscular body along with greater fat mass for resisting opposite reactionary force of shot. Hammer thrower also need greater endomorph body for counteracting centrifugal force while taking turn.

Shot putters are using linear application of force to propel the shot. Therefore the requirement of endomorph body for shot putter is greater than hammer throwers. In discus throw principles of aerodynamics are used. Discus throwers are less endomorphic in comparison to shot putters and hammer throwers. Discus throwers require greater speed during turning movement. Therefore the requirement of endomorphy for discus throwers is lesser than shot putters and hammers. Javelin also moves under the principles of aerodynamics. As the weight of javelin is only 800 grams therefore the requirement of maximum strength is not there. Javelin throwers need not only greater power to execute the throw to maximum distance they need a natural shoulder jerk. Therefore they are having lesser

endomorphs to shot putters, hammer throwers and discus throwers.

Long jumpers also need maximum explosive power to take powerful take off while jumping the greater endomorphy also helps him to create greater momentum in flight phase and propelling body to longer distance. The pole vaulters also need an adequate level of endomorphy to create momentum while lifting the body into the air with the help of pole and take swing. However lesser endomorphs than shot putters, hammer, discus, javelin throwers and long jumpers. The mean endomorphy of triple and high jumpers were lower than other, this might be because of they need greater height and explosive strength while takeoff but greater body weight may disadvantageous for high and triple jumpers.

Mesomorphy

Statistical finding had further revealed that mean Mesomorphy of shot putters was significantly > Mesomorphy of high, triple, long jumpers, pole vaulters, discus, hammer and javelin throwers. Further mean Mesomorphy of Triple, Long jumpers, Pole vaulters and discus throwers were also significantly > High jumpers, hammer and javelin throwers.

Shot putters need maximum explosive strength of all groups to propel the shot to maximum distance. They had to apply linear force on a shot of 7.26 kg therefore muscle girths of shot putters are greater than other jumping and throwing events. The triple jumpers had to take three powerful jumps with in alternate steps to cover maximum of distance. To create these successive powerful jerks they need good muscular in legs and arms jerk of the leg muscles, thus the mesomorphy of the triple jumpers is greater than other groups. The long jumpers also need the powerful take off of the leg muscles but only single time during the jump so the mesomorphy of the long jumpers is less than the triple jump but more than other groups. The pole vaulters also need powerful shoulder muscle for lifting the body weight, therefore mesomorphy of the pole vaulters is more than that of high jumpers but less than that of long and triple jumpers.

Discus throwers need greater speed with power to throw the discus of only 2kg weight, Therefore the requirement of greater muscular girth for maximum strength does not exist much in them in comparison to Shot putters, triple jumpers, long jumpers and pole vaulters. The mesomorphy of the high jumpers is lesser than Shot putters, triple jumpers, long jumpers, pole vaulters and discus throwers because they possess greater upper and lower limb length than the other group's performers, this gives them a higher center of gravity which is a fundamental prerequisite for good performance in high jump.

Ectomorphy

The mean ectomorphy of High jumpers was significantly > Triple jumpers, Pole vaulters, Long jumpers, Javelin, Discus, Hammer throwers and Shot putters. Further mean ectomorphy of triple jumpers

and pole vaulters were also significantly > Long jumpers, Javelin, discus, hammer throwers and shot putters. The mean ectomorphy of long jumpers was significantly > javelin, discus, hammer throwers and shot putters. The mean ectomorphy of the javelin throwers was significantly > discus, hammer throwers and shot putters. The mean ectomorphy of the discus throwers was also significantly > shot putters.

The high jumpers need lighter body weight and higher center of gravity so that they can achieve more height with minimum use of muscle power for lifting their center of gravity higher, thus the greater ectomorphy of high jumpers than the mean ectomorphy of Triple jumpers, Pole vaulters, Long jumpers, Javelin throwers, Discus throwers, Hammer throwers and Shot putters is significantly helpful in enhancing their performance.

Shot putters are using linear application of force whereas hammer throwers and Discus throwers use centrifugal force to propel their respective implements. Less Ectomorphy of Hammer and Discus thrower is compensated by getting more stability. The excess ectomorphy of javelin thrower helps in efficient execution of technique and creation of powerful shoulder jerk.

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